

GREEN MARKETING AND ITS IMPACT ON CUSTOMERS SATISFACTION IN INDIA

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Abstract: Green marketing is a concept which is concerned with protection of environment, bio-diversity and for sustainable development. Traditional marketing brings lots of problem for environment. It destroys the bio-diversity and depletes the Ozone layer. Gas which is using in air-conditions and refrigerators are the main source which depletes the Ozone layer. The manufacturing process is also harmful for the planet. Packaging material creates huge pollution for the environment. To avoid these problems companies are focusing towards green marketing. Although it is an expensive deal for the companies in initial stage but in long run companies earn good profit. It also provides competitive advantage. Now-a-days customers are more environments conscious and they started to use eco-friendly products.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Bio-diversity, Recycle, Logistics, Prospective Customers.

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Introduction

Companies produce goods and services to sell them in market. For producing products they follow a particular process. If produce product and production process is environment friendly then it is called as Green marketing. In green marketing manufacturers produce product in sustainable manner. They avoid using toxic materials which can be harmful to the environment. Companies' use those products which can be recycle after their use or which can be produce by recycle process. These both processes are helpful in reducing pollution. If the produce product require packaging in green marketing that packaging is also follow the rules of green marketing and sustainable development. Green marketing is a basic characteristic of corporate social responsible and sustainable development companies. In green marketing companies spend money on those activities which are kinder to the earth. This kind of marketing is very expensive in comparison to traditional marketing. But due to increasing demand to eco-friendly products these companies are capable to increase their profits. Government also support to such organizations which opt go green practices and provide subsidies and other benefits. Such government supports are play as an important motivation factors for these organizations.

Objectives of Green Marketing

The basic objectives of green marketing are as below:

- **Reduce Pollution:** Companies who are going green are conscious about environment. They try to minimize pollution at every level from raw material to finish goods. Procuring raw material of high and good quality, high tech machineries to convert it into finish goods, minimizing use of packaging material according to necessity can be few methods to reduce pollution.
- **Recycle Product:** Once a product is used companies can ask for reverse marketing so that used material can be recycled. Poly bags, glass bottles, papers etc. can be recycled by the organizations. It can reduce wastes as well as save the environment.
- **Reuse:** Companies go for reusing for those products directly which go for little processing like glass bottle. Mostly soft drink companies ask customers to return the glass bottles. These soft drink companies wash them thoroughly and use them again to fill beverages.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Companies use those processes and machinery which are energy saving. Using natural resources as a source of energy is a good option for them. Using solar energy reduce energy consumption at a great extent.
- **Sustainable Development:** Going green is also focused on sustainable development. Companies should use the natural material in such a way so that it can be saving for future use. Thinking for future and acting for present is important.
- **Save Bio-diversity:** Bio-diversity is a big treasure. Companies need to work to save bio-diversity. Reduction in water

pollution, air pollution, soil pollution and noise pollution is important step in this direction.

Marketing Strategies for Green Marketing

Going green is very important and useful tool for those companies who want to differentiate their products from competitors, who want to build a positive image in customer's mind, who want to run for long time etc. but going green is not similar to traditional marketing. Going green is comparatively expensive and companies need to create awareness regarding their initiatives and efforts. There are following marketing strategies for going green:

- **Energy Efficient Products:** Companies should design those products which are energy efficient. Companies can use natural energy resources to produce energy such as; wind energy, water energy and solar energy. Solar panels are highly in use by energy efficient and energy conscious companies. These products decrease their energy consumption on a remarkable level.
- **Right Positioning:** If company is using going green practices then it should position itself in right direction. Its positioning should give a clear picture that company is producing eco-friendly products and use eco-friendly processes. Company should differentiate its products from competitors' products. It should show its environment concern.
- **Pricing Strategy:** Green pricing is an effective tool to set the price as going green. Going green reduce the product price. Customer can avail products and services at lower price. Example using CNG cars, electronic vehicles etc. reduces the price for customers.
- **New ways in Logistics:** Using green logistics is effective for going green. Company can use recycle packaging to reduce waste.

Importance of Green Marketing

Green Marketing is not only beneficial for the environment but it is also beneficial for the company. As the process of going green is expensive for the organizations but due to increasing awareness of customers towards their environment companies start to earn profit in long run. There can be following areas which are where companies can be benefited by using green marketing practices:

- **Developing New Markets:** Green marketing products is an emerging market. Customers are highly conscious towards their environment. They use and support those products which are eco-friendly and less harmful to the planet. Now customers are shifting their choices towards these products.
- **Brand Loyalty:** Companies which are producing eco-friendly products and using eco-friendly practices they are able to build a good brand image in customers mind, and customers also loyal towards such companies. This is because it gives a sense of "doing good for the society".
- **Competitive Advantages:** Green marketing provides competitive edge to the companies. In comparison to traditional marketing products green marketing products are highly in demand. Increasing environment awareness, a sense of good citizen of the country etc. are the reasons which are influencing customers purchase behavior. So customers are shifting their preferences from traditional marketing products to green marketing products.
- **Positive Public Image:** Opting green marketing practices by the companies deliver the message among the customers that company is responsible towards its society and environment. This creates a positive image of the company in existing and prospective customers.

Conclusion

Green marketing is an effective tool for competitive advantages and sustainable development. It shows that company is environment conscious and effectively participates in corporate social responsibility. This builds a good brand image and spread a positive mouth of publicity. With a good brand image company can enjoy its brand equity. In India companies have huge opportunities. Government also support to those organizations which involve in such practices. Go green practices mostly work on 3R; Reuse, Recycle and Reduce.

References

1. Dr. Aparna P Goyal, Environment-Friendly Products-Adapt Green Now: Green Marketing
2. J. Keegan Warren and C. Green Marketing, Global Marketing
3. Jacquelyn A. Ottman, The New Rules of Green Marketing: Strategies, Tools, and Inspiration for Sustainable Branding
4. Jeff Keller, Attitude Is Everything: Change Your Attitude ... Change Your Life!
5. Monica Loss, Green Marketing, Marketing Strategies and Consumer Behavior
6. Robert Dahlstrom, Green Marketing Management
7. <https://learn.g2.com>
8. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org>
9. <https://www.firstcarbonsolutions.com>
10. <https://www.iisd.org>

11. <https://www.investopedia.com>
12. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
13. <https://www.shopify.in>
14. <https://www.thebalancesmb.com>
15. www.sd-commission.org.uk